

APPENDIX K FOR THE DOSSIER: A HYPOTHESIS FOR THE ELABORATION OF HEPTATONIC SCALES

COMPLETE DATABASE OF THE 17TH OF THE OCTAVE GENERATIONS FOR NI = 7 (HEPTATONIC SCALES) WITH THE COMPLETE ALPHABET '1' TO '17'

This appendix is not included in the printed version of NEMO-Online Vol. 4. The following are raw results (slightly rearranged) from program Modes V. 5.2.

calcul n° 6 ; ni = 7 ; hyper = 38 ; sys. = 1144 ; sous-sys. = 8008 ; imax_calc = 11	hyper n° 18 ; val.: 1 1 1 2 2 5 5 ; RC = 8712	RC = 8019
	hyper n° 19 ; val.: 1 1 1 2 3 3 6 ; RC = 7800	hyper n° 37 ; val.: 2 2 2 2 2 3 4 ; RC = 8505
hyper n° 1 ; val.: 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 ; RC = 1984	hyper n° 20 ; val.: 1 1 1 2 3 4 5 ; RC = 9240	hyper n° 38 ; val.: 2 2 2 2 3 3 3 ; RC = 10125
hyper n° 2 ; val.: 1 1 1 1 2 10 ; RC = 2784	hyper n° 21 ; val.: 1 1 1 2 4 4 4 ; RC = 8232	hyper n° 1 ; val.: 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 ; RC = 1984
hyper n° 3 ; val.: 1 1 1 1 1 3 9 ; RC = 3680	hyper n° 22 ; val.: 1 1 1 3 3 3 5 ; RC = 11000	sys.: 1 ; imin = 1 ; imax_hyp = 11 (1 ; 1 ; 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 1)
hyper n° 4 ; val.: 1 1 1 1 1 4 8 ; RC = 4256	hyper n° 23 ; val.: 1 1 1 3 3 4 4 ; RC = 9800	hyper n° 2 ; val.: 1 1 1 1 2 10 ; RC = 2784
hyper n° 5 ; val.: 1 1 1 1 1 5 7 ; RC = 5984	hyper n° 24 ; val.: 1 1 2 2 2 2 7 ; RC = 5508	sys.: 6 ; imin = 1 ; imax_hyp = 10 (2 ; 1 ; 1 1 1 1 2 10) (2 ; 2 ; 1 1 1 1 1 10 2) (2 ; 3 ; 1 1 1 2 1 10) (2 ; 4 ; 1 1 1 1 10 1 2) (2 ; 5 ; 1 1 1 2 1 1 10) (2 ; 6 ; 1 1 1 1 10 1 2)
hyper n° 6 ; val.: 1 1 1 1 1 6 6 ; RC = 5408	hyper n° 25 ; val.: 1 1 2 2 2 3 6 ; RC = 7020	hyper n° 3 ; val.: 1 1 1 1 1 3 9 ; RC = 3680
hyper n° 7 ; val.: 1 1 1 1 2 2 9 ; RC = 3312	hyper n° 26 ; val.: 1 1 2 2 2 4 5 ; RC = 8316	sys.: 6 ; imin = 1 ; imax_hyp = 9 (3 ; 1 ; 1 1 1 1 1 3 9) (3 ; 2 ; 1 1 1 1 1 9 3) (3 ; 3 ; 1 1 1 1 3 1 9) (3 ; 4 ; 1 1 1 1 9 1 3) (3 ; 5 ; 1 1 1 3 1 1 9) (3 ; 6 ; 1 1 1 9 1 1 3)
hyper n° 8 ; val.: 1 1 1 1 2 3 8 ; RC = 4560	hyper n° 27 ; val.: 1 1 2 2 3 3 5 ; RC = 9900	hyper n° 4 ; val.: 1 1 1 1 1 4 8 ; RC = 4256
hyper n° 9 ; val.: 1 1 1 1 2 4 7 ; RC = 5712	hyper n° 28 ; val.: 1 1 2 2 3 4 4 ; RC = 8820	sys.: 6 ; imin = 1 ; imax_hyp = 8 (4 ; 1 ; 1 1 1 1 1 4 8) (4 ; 2 ; 1 1 1 1 1 8 4) (4 ; 3 ; 1 1 1 1 4 1 8)
hyper n° 10 ; val.: 1 1 1 1 2 5 6 ; RC = 6864	hyper n° 29 ; val.: 1 1 2 3 3 3 4 ; RC = 10500	
hyper n° 11 ; val.: 1 1 1 1 3 3 7 ; RC = 6800	hyper n° 30 ; val.: 1 1 3 3 3 3 3 ; RC = 12500	
hyper n° 12 ; val.: 1 1 1 1 3 4 6 ; RC = 7280	hyper n° 31 ; val.: 1 2 2 2 2 2 6 ; RC = 6318	
hyper n° 13 ; val.: 1 1 1 1 3 5 5 ; RC = 9680	hyper n° 32 ; val.: 1 2 2 2 2 3 5 ; RC = 8910	
hyper n° 14 ; val.: 1 1 1 1 4 4 5 ; RC = 8624	hyper n° 33 ; val.: 1 2 2 2 2 4 4 ; RC = 7938	
hyper n° 15 ; val.: 1 1 1 2 2 2 8 ; RC = 4104	hyper n° 34 ; val.: 1 2 2 2 3 3 4 ; RC = 9450	
hyper n° 16 ; val.: 1 1 1 2 2 3 7 ; RC = 6120	hyper n° 35 ; val.: 1 2 2 3 3 3 3 ; RC = 11250	
hyper n° 17 ; val.: 1 1 1 2 2 4 6 ; RC = 6552	hyper n° 36 ; val.: 2 2 2 2 2 2 5 ;	

(4;4;1111814)	(8;6;1111832)	(9;20;1121174)
(4;5;1114118)	(8;7;1112138)	(9;21;1121417)
(4;6;1118114)	(8;8;1112183)	(9;22;1121714)
	(8;9;1112318)	(9;23;1124117)
hyper n° 5; val.: 1111157;	(8;10;1112813)	(9;24;1127114)
RC = 5984	(8;11;1113128)	(9;25;1141172)
sys.: 6; imin = 1; imax_hyp = 7	(8;12;1113182)	(9;26;1141217)
(5;1;1111157)	(8;13;1113218)	(9;27;1141712)
(5;2;1111175)	(8;14;1113812)	(9;28;1142117)
(5;3;1111517)	(8;15;1118123)	(9;29;1171214)
(5;4;1111715)	(8;16;1118132)	(9;30;1171412)
(5;5;1115117)	(8;17;1118213)	
(5;6;1117115)	(8;18;1118312)	hyper n° 10; val.: 1111256;
	(8;19;1121138)	RC = 6864
hyper n° 6; val.: 1111166;	(8;20;1121183)	sys.: 30; imin = 1; imax_hyp = 6
RC = 5408	(8;21;1121318)	(10;1;1111256)
sys.: 3; imin = 1; imax_hyp = 6	(8;22;1121813)	(10;2;1111265)
(6;1;1111166)	(8;23;1123118)	(10;3;1111526)
(6;2;1111616)	(8;24;1128113)	(10;4;1111562)
(6;3;1116116)	(8;25;1131182)	(10;5;1111625)
	(8;26;1131218)	(10;6;1111652)
hyper n° 7; val.: 1111229;	(8;27;1131812)	(10;7;1112156)
RC = 3312	(8;28;1132118)	(10;8;1112165)
sys.: 15; imin = 1; imax_hyp = 9	(8;29;1181213)	(10;9;1112516)
(7;1;1111229)	(8;30;1181312)	(10;10;1112615)
(7;2;1111292)		(10;11;1115126)
(7;3;1111922)	hyper n° 9; val.: 1111247;	(10;12;1115162)
(7;4;1112129)	RC = 5712	(10;13;1115216)
(7;5;1112192)	sys.: 30; imin = 1; imax_hyp = 7	(10;14;1115612)
(7;6;1112219)	(9;1;1111247)	(10;15;1116125)
(7;7;1112912)	(9;2;1111274)	(10;16;1116152)
(7;8;1119122)	(9;3;1111427)	(10;17;1116215)
(7;9;1119212)	(9;4;1111472)	(10;18;1116512)
(7;10;1121129)	(9;5;1111724)	(10;19;1121156)
(7;11;1121192)	(9;6;1111742)	(10;20;1121165)
(7;12;1121219)	(9;7;1112147)	(10;21;1121516)
(7;13;1121912)	(9;8;1112174)	(10;22;1121615)
(7;14;1122119)	(9;9;1112417)	(10;23;1125116)
(7;15;1191212)	(9;10;1112714)	(10;24;1126115)
	(9;11;1114127)	(10;25;1151162)
hyper n° 8; val.: 1111238;	(9;12;1114172)	(10;26;1151216)
RC = 4560	(9;13;1114217)	(10;27;1151612)
sys.: 30; imin = 1; imax_hyp = 8	(9;14;1114712)	(10;28;1152116)
(8;1;1111238)	(9;15;1117124)	(10;29;1161215)
(8;2;1111283)	(9;16;1117142)	(10;30;1161512)
(8;3;1111328)	(9;17;1117214)	
(8;4;1111382)	(9;18;1117412)	hyper n° 11; val.: 1111337;
(8;5;1111823)	(9;19;1121147)	RC = 6800

sys.: 15; imin = 1; imax_hyp = 7	(12; 29; 1 1 6 1 3 1 4)	(15; 5; 1 1 2 1 2 2 8)
(11; 1; 1 1 1 1 3 3 7)	(12; 30; 1 1 6 1 4 1 3)	(15; 6; 1 1 2 1 2 8 2)
(11; 2; 1 1 1 1 3 7 3)		(15; 7; 1 1 2 1 8 2 2)
(11; 3; 1 1 1 1 7 3 3)	hyper n° 13; val.: 1 1 1 1 3 5 5;	(15; 8; 1 1 2 2 1 2 8)
(11; 4; 1 1 1 3 1 3 7)	RC = 9680	(15; 9; 1 1 2 2 1 8 2)
(11; 5; 1 1 1 3 1 7 3)	sys.: 15; imin = 1; imax_hyp = 5	(15; 10; 1 1 2 2 2 1 8)
(11; 6; 1 1 1 3 3 1 7)	(13; 1; 1 1 1 1 3 5 5)	(15; 11; 1 1 2 2 8 1 2)
(11; 7; 1 1 1 3 7 1 3)	(13; 2; 1 1 1 1 5 3 5)	(15; 12; 1 1 2 8 1 2 2)
(11; 8; 1 1 1 7 1 3 3)	(13; 3; 1 1 1 1 5 5 3)	(15; 13; 1 1 2 8 2 1 2)
(11; 9; 1 1 1 7 3 1 3)	(13; 4; 1 1 1 3 1 5 5)	(15; 14; 1 1 8 1 2 2 2)
(11; 10; 1 1 3 1 1 3 7)	(13; 5; 1 1 1 3 5 1 5)	(15; 15; 1 1 8 2 1 2 2)
(11; 11; 1 1 3 1 1 7 3)	(13; 6; 1 1 1 5 1 3 5)	(15; 16; 1 1 8 2 2 1 2)
(11; 12; 1 1 3 1 3 1 7)	(13; 7; 1 1 1 5 1 5 3)	(15; 17; 1 2 1 2 1 2 8)
(11; 13; 1 1 3 1 7 1 3)	(13; 8; 1 1 1 5 3 1 5)	(15; 18; 1 2 1 2 1 8 2)
(11; 14; 1 1 3 3 1 1 7)	(13; 9; 1 1 1 5 5 1 3)	(15; 19; 1 2 1 2 2 1 8)
(11; 15; 1 1 7 1 3 1 3)	(13; 10; 1 1 3 1 1 5 5)	(15; 20; 1 2 1 8 1 2 2)
	(13; 11; 1 1 3 1 5 1 5)	
hyper n° 12; val.: 1 1 1 1 3 4 6;	(13; 12; 1 1 3 5 1 1 5)	hyper n° 16; val.: 1 1 1 2 2 3 7;
RC = 7280	(13; 13; 1 1 5 1 1 5 3)	RC = 6120
sys.: 30; imin = 1; imax_hyp = 6	(13; 14; 1 1 5 1 3 1 5)	sys.: 60; imin = 1; imax_hyp = 7
(12; 1; 1 1 1 1 3 4 6)	(13; 15; 1 1 5 1 5 1 3)	(16; 1; 1 1 1 2 2 3 7)
(12; 2; 1 1 1 1 3 6 4)		(16; 2; 1 1 1 2 2 7 3)
(12; 3; 1 1 1 1 4 3 6)	hyper n° 14; val.: 1 1 1 1 4 4 5;	(16; 3; 1 1 1 2 3 2 7)
(12; 4; 1 1 1 1 4 6 3)	RC = 8624	(16; 4; 1 1 1 2 3 7 2)
(12; 5; 1 1 1 1 6 3 4)	sys.: 15; imin = 1; imax_hyp = 5	(16; 5; 1 1 1 2 7 2 3)
(12; 6; 1 1 1 1 6 4 3)	(14; 1; 1 1 1 1 4 4 5)	(16; 6; 1 1 1 2 7 3 2)
(12; 7; 1 1 1 3 1 4 6)	(14; 2; 1 1 1 1 4 5 4)	(16; 7; 1 1 1 3 2 2 7)
(12; 8; 1 1 1 3 1 6 4)	(14; 3; 1 1 1 1 5 4 4)	(16; 8; 1 1 1 3 2 7 2)
(12; 9; 1 1 1 3 4 1 6)	(14; 4; 1 1 1 4 1 4 5)	(16; 9; 1 1 1 3 7 2 2)
(12; 10; 1 1 1 3 6 1 4)	(14; 5; 1 1 1 4 1 5 4)	(16; 10; 1 1 1 7 2 2 3)
(12; 11; 1 1 1 4 1 3 6)	(14; 6; 1 1 1 4 4 1 5)	(16; 11; 1 1 1 7 2 3 2)
(12; 12; 1 1 1 4 1 6 3)	(14; 7; 1 1 1 4 5 1 4)	(16; 12; 1 1 1 7 3 2 2)
(12; 13; 1 1 1 4 3 1 6)	(14; 8; 1 1 1 5 1 4 4)	(16; 13; 1 1 2 1 2 3 7)
(12; 14; 1 1 1 4 6 1 3)	(14; 9; 1 1 1 5 4 1 4)	(16; 14; 1 1 2 1 2 7 3)
(12; 15; 1 1 1 6 1 3 4)	(14; 10; 1 1 4 1 1 4 5)	(16; 15; 1 1 2 1 3 2 7)
(12; 16; 1 1 1 6 1 4 3)	(14; 11; 1 1 4 1 1 5 4)	(16; 16; 1 1 2 1 3 7 2)
(12; 17; 1 1 1 6 3 1 4)	(14; 12; 1 1 4 1 4 1 5)	(16; 17; 1 1 2 1 7 2 3)
(12; 18; 1 1 1 6 4 1 3)	(14; 13; 1 1 4 1 5 1 4)	(16; 18; 1 1 2 1 7 3 2)
(12; 19; 1 1 3 1 1 4 6)	(14; 14; 1 1 4 4 1 1 5)	(16; 19; 1 1 2 2 1 3 7)
(12; 20; 1 1 3 1 1 6 4)	(14; 15; 1 1 5 1 4 1 4)	(16; 20; 1 1 2 2 1 7 3)
(12; 21; 1 1 3 1 4 1 6)		(16; 21; 1 1 2 2 3 1 7)
(12; 22; 1 1 3 1 6 1 4)	hyper n° 15; val.: 1 1 1 2 2 2 8;	(16; 22; 1 1 2 2 7 1 3)
(12; 23; 1 1 3 4 1 1 6)	RC = 4104	(16; 23; 1 1 2 3 1 2 7)
(12; 24; 1 1 3 6 1 1 4)	sys.: 20; imin = 1; imax_hyp = 8	(16; 24; 1 1 2 3 1 7 2)
(12; 25; 1 1 4 1 1 6 3)	(15; 1; 1 1 1 2 2 2 8)	(16; 25; 1 1 2 3 2 1 7)
(12; 26; 1 1 4 1 3 1 6)	(15; 2; 1 1 1 2 2 8 2)	(16; 26; 1 1 2 3 7 1 2)
(12; 27; 1 1 4 1 6 1 3)	(15; 3; 1 1 1 2 8 2 2)	(16; 27; 1 1 2 7 1 2 3)
(12; 28; 1 1 4 3 1 1 6)	(15; 4; 1 1 1 8 2 2 2)	(16; 28; 1 1 2 7 1 3 2)

(16; 29; 1 1 2 7 2 1 3)	(17; 13; 1 1 2 1 2 4 6)	
(16; 30; 1 1 2 7 3 1 2)	(17; 14; 1 1 2 1 2 6 4)	hyper n° 18; val.: 1 1 1 2 2 5 5;
(16; 31; 1 1 3 1 2 2 7)	(17; 15; 1 1 2 1 4 2 6)	RC = 8712
(16; 32; 1 1 3 1 2 7 2)	(17; 16; 1 1 2 1 4 6 2)	sys.: 30; imin = 1; imax_hyp = 5
(16; 33; 1 1 3 1 7 2 2)	(17; 17; 1 1 2 1 6 2 4)	(18; 1; 1 1 1 2 2 5 5)
(16; 34; 1 1 3 2 1 2 7)	(17; 18; 1 1 2 1 6 4 2)	(18; 2; 1 1 1 2 5 2 5)
(16; 35; 1 1 3 2 1 7 2)	(17; 19; 1 1 2 2 1 4 6)	(18; 3; 1 1 1 2 5 5 2)
(16; 36; 1 1 3 2 2 1 7)	(17; 20; 1 1 2 2 1 6 4)	(18; 4; 1 1 1 5 2 2 5)
(16; 37; 1 1 3 2 7 1 2)	(17; 21; 1 1 2 2 4 1 6)	(18; 5; 1 1 1 5 2 5 2)
(16; 38; 1 1 3 7 1 2 2)	(17; 22; 1 1 2 2 6 1 4)	(18; 6; 1 1 1 5 5 2 2)
(16; 39; 1 1 3 7 2 1 2)	(17; 23; 1 1 2 4 1 2 6)	(18; 7; 1 1 2 1 2 5 5)
(16; 40; 1 1 7 1 2 2 3)	(17; 24; 1 1 2 4 1 6 2)	(18; 8; 1 1 2 1 5 2 5)
(16; 41; 1 1 7 1 2 3 2)	(17; 25; 1 1 2 4 2 1 6)	(18; 9; 1 1 2 1 5 5 2)
(16; 42; 1 1 7 1 3 2 2)	(17; 26; 1 1 2 4 6 1 2)	(18; 10; 1 1 2 2 1 5 5)
(16; 43; 1 1 7 2 1 2 3)	(17; 27; 1 1 2 6 1 2 4)	(18; 11; 1 1 2 2 5 1 5)
(16; 44; 1 1 7 2 1 3 2)	(17; 28; 1 1 2 6 1 4 2)	(18; 12; 1 1 2 5 1 2 5)
(16; 45; 1 1 7 2 2 1 3)	(17; 29; 1 1 2 6 2 1 4)	(18; 13; 1 1 2 5 1 5 2)
(16; 46; 1 1 7 2 3 1 2)	(17; 30; 1 1 2 6 4 1 2)	(18; 14; 1 1 2 5 2 1 5)
(16; 47; 1 1 7 3 1 2 2)	(17; 31; 1 1 4 1 2 2 6)	(18; 15; 1 1 2 5 5 1 2)
(16; 48; 1 1 7 3 2 1 2)	(17; 32; 1 1 4 1 2 6 2)	(18; 16; 1 1 5 1 2 2 5)
(16; 49; 1 2 1 2 1 3 7)	(17; 33; 1 1 4 1 6 2 2)	(18; 17; 1 1 5 1 2 5 2)
(16; 50; 1 2 1 2 1 7 3)	(17; 34; 1 1 4 2 1 2 6)	(18; 18; 1 1 5 1 5 2 2)
(16; 51; 1 2 1 2 3 1 7)	(17; 35; 1 1 4 2 1 6 2)	(18; 19; 1 1 5 2 1 2 5)
(16; 52; 1 2 1 2 7 1 3)	(17; 36; 1 1 4 2 2 1 6)	(18; 20; 1 1 5 2 1 5 2)
(16; 53; 1 2 1 3 1 2 7)	(17; 37; 1 1 4 2 6 1 2)	(18; 21; 1 1 5 2 2 1 5)
(16; 54; 1 2 1 3 1 7 2)	(17; 38; 1 1 4 6 1 2 2)	(18; 22; 1 1 5 2 5 1 2)
(16; 55; 1 2 1 3 2 1 7)	(17; 39; 1 1 4 6 2 1 2)	(18; 23; 1 1 5 5 1 2 2)
(16; 56; 1 2 1 7 1 2 3)	(17; 40; 1 1 6 1 2 2 4)	(18; 24; 1 1 5 5 2 1 2)
(16; 57; 1 2 1 7 1 3 2)	(17; 41; 1 1 6 1 2 4 2)	(18; 25; 1 2 1 2 1 5 5)
(16; 58; 1 2 1 7 2 1 3)	(17; 42; 1 1 6 1 4 2 2)	(18; 26; 1 2 1 2 5 1 5)
(16; 59; 1 2 2 1 3 1 7)	(17; 43; 1 1 6 2 1 2 4)	(18; 27; 1 2 1 5 1 2 5)
(16; 60; 1 2 2 1 7 1 3)	(17; 44; 1 1 6 2 1 4 2)	(18; 28; 1 2 1 5 1 5 2)
	(17; 45; 1 1 6 2 2 1 4)	(18; 29; 1 2 1 5 2 1 5)
hyper n° 17; val.: 1 1 1 2 2 4 6;	(17; 46; 1 1 6 2 4 1 2)	(18; 30; 1 2 2 1 5 1 5)
RC = 6552	(17; 47; 1 1 6 4 1 2 2)	
sys.: 60; imin = 1; imax_hyp = 6	(17; 48; 1 1 6 4 2 1 2)	hyper n° 19; val.: 1 1 1 2 3 3 6;
(17; 1; 1 1 1 2 2 4 6)	(17; 49; 1 2 1 2 1 4 6)	RC = 7800
(17; 2; 1 1 1 2 2 6 4)	(17; 50; 1 2 1 2 1 6 4)	sys.: 60; imin = 1; imax_hyp = 6
(17; 3; 1 1 1 2 4 2 6)	(17; 51; 1 2 1 2 4 1 6)	(19; 1; 1 1 1 2 3 3 6)
(17; 4; 1 1 1 2 4 6 2)	(17; 52; 1 2 1 2 6 1 4)	(19; 2; 1 1 1 2 3 6 3)
(17; 5; 1 1 1 2 6 2 4)	(17; 53; 1 2 1 4 1 2 6)	(19; 3; 1 1 1 2 6 3 3)
(17; 6; 1 1 1 2 6 4 2)	(17; 54; 1 2 1 4 1 6 2)	(19; 4; 1 1 1 3 2 3 6)
(17; 7; 1 1 1 4 2 2 6)	(17; 55; 1 2 1 4 2 1 6)	(19; 5; 1 1 1 3 2 6 3)
(17; 8; 1 1 1 4 2 6 2)	(17; 56; 1 2 1 6 1 2 4)	(19; 6; 1 1 1 3 3 2 6)
(17; 9; 1 1 1 4 6 2 2)	(17; 57; 1 2 1 6 1 4 2)	(19; 7; 1 1 1 3 3 6 2)
(17; 10; 1 1 1 6 2 2 4)	(17; 58; 1 2 1 6 2 1 4)	(19; 8; 1 1 1 3 6 2 3)
(17; 11; 1 1 1 6 2 4 2)	(17; 59; 1 2 2 1 4 1 6)	(19; 9; 1 1 1 3 6 3 2)
(17; 12; 1 1 1 6 4 2 2)	(17; 60; 1 2 2 1 6 1 4)	(19; 10; 1 1 1 6 2 3 3)

(19; 11; 1 1 1 6 3 2 3)	(19; 59; 1 3 1 3 2 1 6)	(20; 43; 1 1 3 1 2 4 5)
(19; 12; 1 1 1 6 3 3 2)	(19; 60; 1 3 1 6 1 3 2)	(20; 44; 1 1 3 1 2 5 4)
(19; 13; 1 1 2 1 3 3 6)		(20; 45; 1 1 3 1 4 2 5)
(19; 14; 1 1 2 1 3 6 3)	hyper n° 20; val.: 1 1 1 2 3 4 5;	(20; 46; 1 1 3 1 4 5 2)
(19; 15; 1 1 2 1 6 3 3)	RC = 9240	(20; 47; 1 1 3 1 5 2 4)
(19; 16; 1 1 2 3 1 3 6)	sys.: 120; imin = 1; imax_hyp = 5	(20; 48; 1 1 3 1 5 4 2)
(19; 17; 1 1 2 3 1 6 3)	(20; 1; 1 1 1 2 3 4 5)	(20; 49; 1 1 3 2 1 4 5)
(19; 18; 1 1 2 3 3 1 6)	(20; 2; 1 1 1 2 3 5 4)	(20; 50; 1 1 3 2 1 5 4)
(19; 19; 1 1 2 3 6 1 3)	(20; 3; 1 1 1 2 4 3 5)	(20; 51; 1 1 3 2 4 1 5)
(19; 20; 1 1 2 6 1 3 3)	(20; 4; 1 1 1 2 4 5 3)	(20; 52; 1 1 3 2 5 1 4)
(19; 21; 1 1 2 6 3 1 3)	(20; 5; 1 1 1 2 5 3 4)	(20; 53; 1 1 3 4 1 2 5)
(19; 22; 1 1 3 1 2 3 6)	(20; 6; 1 1 1 2 5 4 3)	(20; 54; 1 1 3 4 1 5 2)
(19; 23; 1 1 3 1 2 6 3)	(20; 7; 1 1 1 3 2 4 5)	(20; 55; 1 1 3 4 2 1 5)
(19; 24; 1 1 3 1 3 2 6)	(20; 8; 1 1 1 3 2 5 4)	(20; 56; 1 1 3 4 5 1 2)
(19; 25; 1 1 3 1 3 6 2)	(20; 9; 1 1 1 3 4 2 5)	(20; 57; 1 1 3 5 1 2 4)
(19; 26; 1 1 3 1 6 2 3)	(20; 10; 1 1 1 3 4 5 2)	(20; 58; 1 1 3 5 1 4 2)
(19; 27; 1 1 3 1 6 3 2)	(20; 11; 1 1 1 3 5 2 4)	(20; 59; 1 1 3 5 2 1 4)
(19; 28; 1 1 3 2 1 3 6)	(20; 12; 1 1 1 3 5 4 2)	(20; 60; 1 1 3 5 4 1 2)
(19; 29; 1 1 3 2 1 6 3)	(20; 13; 1 1 1 4 2 3 5)	(20; 61; 1 1 4 1 2 3 5)
(19; 30; 1 1 3 2 3 1 6)	(20; 14; 1 1 1 4 2 5 3)	(20; 62; 1 1 4 1 2 5 3)
(19; 31; 1 1 3 2 6 1 3)	(20; 15; 1 1 1 4 3 2 5)	(20; 63; 1 1 4 1 3 2 5)
(19; 32; 1 1 3 3 1 2 6)	(20; 16; 1 1 1 4 3 5 2)	(20; 64; 1 1 4 1 3 5 2)
(19; 33; 1 1 3 3 1 6 2)	(20; 17; 1 1 1 4 5 2 3)	(20; 65; 1 1 4 1 5 2 3)
(19; 34; 1 1 3 3 2 1 6)	(20; 18; 1 1 1 4 5 3 2)	(20; 66; 1 1 4 1 5 3 2)
(19; 35; 1 1 3 3 6 1 2)	(20; 19; 1 1 1 5 2 3 4)	(20; 67; 1 1 4 2 1 3 5)
(19; 36; 1 1 3 6 1 2 3)	(20; 20; 1 1 1 5 2 4 3)	(20; 68; 1 1 4 2 1 5 3)
(19; 37; 1 1 3 6 1 3 2)	(20; 21; 1 1 1 5 3 2 4)	(20; 69; 1 1 4 2 3 1 5)
(19; 38; 1 1 3 6 2 1 3)	(20; 22; 1 1 1 5 3 4 2)	(20; 70; 1 1 4 2 5 1 3)
(19; 39; 1 1 3 6 3 1 2)	(20; 23; 1 1 1 5 4 2 3)	(20; 71; 1 1 4 3 1 2 5)
(19; 40; 1 1 6 1 2 3 3)	(20; 24; 1 1 1 5 4 3 2)	(20; 72; 1 1 4 3 1 5 2)
(19; 41; 1 1 6 1 3 2 3)	(20; 25; 1 1 2 1 3 4 5)	(20; 73; 1 1 4 3 2 1 5)
(19; 42; 1 1 6 1 3 3 2)	(20; 26; 1 1 2 1 3 5 4)	(20; 74; 1 1 4 3 5 1 2)
(19; 43; 1 1 6 2 1 3 3)	(20; 27; 1 1 2 1 4 3 5)	(20; 75; 1 1 4 5 1 2 3)
(19; 44; 1 1 6 2 3 1 3)	(20; 28; 1 1 2 1 4 5 3)	(20; 76; 1 1 4 5 1 3 2)
(19; 45; 1 1 6 3 1 2 3)	(20; 29; 1 1 2 1 5 3 4)	(20; 77; 1 1 4 5 2 1 3)
(19; 46; 1 1 6 3 1 3 2)	(20; 30; 1 1 2 1 5 4 3)	(20; 78; 1 1 4 5 3 1 2)
(19; 47; 1 1 6 3 2 1 3)	(20; 31; 1 1 2 3 1 4 5)	(20; 79; 1 1 5 1 2 3 4)
(19; 48; 1 1 6 3 3 1 2)	(20; 32; 1 1 2 3 1 5 4)	(20; 80; 1 1 5 1 2 4 3)
(19; 49; 1 2 1 3 1 3 6)	(20; 33; 1 1 2 3 4 1 5)	(20; 81; 1 1 5 1 3 2 4)
(19; 50; 1 2 1 3 1 6 3)	(20; 34; 1 1 2 3 5 1 4)	(20; 82; 1 1 5 1 3 4 2)
(19; 51; 1 2 1 3 3 1 6)	(20; 35; 1 1 2 4 1 3 5)	(20; 83; 1 1 5 1 4 2 3)
(19; 52; 1 2 1 3 6 1 3)	(20; 36; 1 1 2 4 1 5 3)	(20; 84; 1 1 5 1 4 3 2)
(19; 53; 1 2 1 6 1 3 3)	(20; 37; 1 1 2 4 3 1 5)	(20; 85; 1 1 5 2 1 3 4)
(19; 54; 1 2 1 6 3 1 3)	(20; 38; 1 1 2 4 5 1 3)	(20; 86; 1 1 5 2 1 4 3)
(19; 55; 1 2 3 1 3 1 6)	(20; 39; 1 1 2 5 1 3 4)	(20; 87; 1 1 5 2 3 1 4)
(19; 56; 1 2 3 1 6 1 3)	(20; 40; 1 1 2 5 1 4 3)	(20; 88; 1 1 5 2 4 1 3)
(19; 57; 1 2 6 1 3 1 3)	(20; 41; 1 1 2 5 3 1 4)	(20; 89; 1 1 5 3 1 2 4)
(19; 58; 1 3 1 3 1 6 2)	(20; 42; 1 1 2 5 4 1 3)	(20; 90; 1 1 5 3 1 4 2)

(20; 91; 1 1 5 3 2 1 4)	(21; 15; 1 1 4 4 2 1 4)	(23; 15; 1 1 3 4 4 1 3)
(20; 92; 1 1 5 3 4 1 2)	(21; 16; 1 1 4 4 4 1 2)	(23; 16; 1 1 4 1 3 3 4)
(20; 93; 1 1 5 4 1 2 3)	(21; 17; 1 2 1 4 1 4 4)	(23; 17; 1 1 4 1 3 4 3)
(20; 94; 1 1 5 4 1 3 2)	(21; 18; 1 2 1 4 4 1 4)	(23; 18; 1 1 4 1 4 3 3)
(20; 95; 1 1 5 4 2 1 3)	(21; 19; 1 2 4 1 4 1 4)	(23; 19; 1 1 4 3 1 3 4)
(20; 96; 1 1 5 4 3 1 2)	(21; 20; 1 4 1 4 1 4 2)	(23; 20; 1 1 4 3 1 4 3)
(20; 97; 1 2 1 3 1 4 5)		(23; 21; 1 1 4 3 3 1 4)
(20; 98; 1 2 1 3 1 5 4)	hyper n° 22; val.: 1 1 1 3 3 3 5;	(23; 22; 1 1 4 3 4 1 3)
(20; 99; 1 2 1 3 4 1 5)	RC = 11000	(23; 23; 1 1 4 4 1 3 3)
(20; 100; 1 2 1 3 5 1 4)	sys.: 20; imin = 1; imax_hyp = 5	(23; 24; 1 1 4 4 3 1 3)
(20; 101; 1 2 1 4 1 3 5)	(22; 1; 1 1 1 3 3 3 5)	(23; 25; 1 3 1 3 1 4 4)
(20; 102; 1 2 1 4 1 5 3)	(22; 2; 1 1 1 3 3 5 3)	(23; 26; 1 3 1 3 4 1 4)
(20; 103; 1 2 1 4 3 1 5)	(22; 3; 1 1 1 3 5 3 3)	(23; 27; 1 3 1 4 1 3 4)
(20; 104; 1 2 1 4 5 1 3)	(22; 4; 1 1 1 5 3 3 3)	(23; 28; 1 3 1 4 1 4 3)
(20; 105; 1 2 1 5 1 3 4)	(22; 5; 1 1 3 1 3 3 5)	(23; 29; 1 3 1 4 3 1 4)
(20; 106; 1 2 1 5 1 4 3)	(22; 6; 1 1 3 1 3 5 3)	(23; 30; 1 3 3 1 4 1 4)
(20; 107; 1 2 1 5 3 1 4)	(22; 7; 1 1 3 1 5 3 3)	
(20; 108; 1 2 1 5 4 1 3)	(22; 8; 1 1 3 3 1 3 5)	hyper n° 24; val.: 1 1 2 2 2 2 7;
(20; 109; 1 2 3 1 4 1 5)	(22; 9; 1 1 3 3 1 5 3)	RC = 5508
(20; 110; 1 2 3 1 5 1 4)	(22; 10; 1 1 3 3 3 1 5)	sys.: 15; imin = 1; imax_hyp = 7
(20; 111; 1 2 4 1 3 1 5)	(22; 11; 1 1 3 3 5 1 3)	(24; 1; 1 1 2 2 2 2 7)
(20; 112; 1 2 4 1 5 1 3)	(22; 12; 1 1 3 5 1 3 3)	(24; 2; 1 1 2 2 2 7 2)
(20; 113; 1 2 5 1 3 1 4)	(22; 13; 1 1 3 5 3 1 3)	(24; 3; 1 1 2 2 7 2 2)
(20; 114; 1 2 5 1 4 1 3)	(22; 14; 1 1 5 1 3 3 3)	(24; 4; 1 1 2 7 2 2 2)
(20; 115; 1 3 1 4 1 5 2)	(22; 15; 1 1 5 3 1 3 3)	(24; 5; 1 1 7 2 2 2 2)
(20; 116; 1 3 1 4 2 1 5)	(22; 16; 1 1 5 3 3 1 3)	(24; 6; 1 2 1 2 2 2 7)
(20; 117; 1 3 1 5 1 4 2)	(22; 17; 1 3 1 3 1 3 5)	(24; 7; 1 2 1 2 2 7 2)
(20; 118; 1 3 1 5 2 1 4)	(22; 18; 1 3 1 3 1 5 3)	(24; 8; 1 2 1 2 7 2 2)
(20; 119; 1 3 2 1 4 1 5)	(22; 19; 1 3 1 3 3 1 5)	(24; 9; 1 2 1 7 2 2 2)
(20; 120; 1 3 2 1 5 1 4)	(22; 20; 1 3 1 5 1 3 3)	(24; 10; 1 2 2 1 2 2 7)
		(24; 11; 1 2 2 1 2 7 2)
hyper n° 21; val.: 1 1 1 2 4 4 4;	hyper n° 23; val.: 1 1 1 3 3 4 4;	(24; 12; 1 2 2 1 7 2 2)
RC = 8232	RC = 9800	(24; 13; 1 2 2 2 1 2 7)
sys.: 20; imin = 1; imax_hyp = 4	sys.: 30; imin = 1; imax_hyp = 4	(24; 14; 1 2 2 2 1 7 2)
(21; 1; 1 1 1 2 4 4 4)	(23; 1; 1 1 1 3 3 4 4)	(24; 15; 1 2 2 2 2 1 7)
(21; 2; 1 1 1 4 2 4 4)	(23; 2; 1 1 1 3 4 3 4)	
(21; 3; 1 1 1 4 4 2 4)	(23; 3; 1 1 1 3 4 4 3)	hyper n° 25; val.: 1 1 2 2 2 3 6;
(21; 4; 1 1 1 4 4 4 2)	(23; 4; 1 1 1 4 3 3 4)	RC = 7020
(21; 5; 1 1 2 1 4 4 4)	(23; 5; 1 1 1 4 3 4 3)	sys.: 60; imin = 1; imax_hyp = 6
(21; 6; 1 1 2 4 1 4 4)	(23; 6; 1 1 1 4 4 3 3)	(25; 1; 1 1 2 2 2 3 6)
(21; 7; 1 1 2 4 4 1 4)	(23; 7; 1 1 3 1 3 4 4)	(25; 2; 1 1 2 2 2 6 3)
(21; 8; 1 1 4 1 2 4 4)	(23; 8; 1 1 3 1 4 3 4)	(25; 3; 1 1 2 2 3 2 6)
(21; 9; 1 1 4 1 4 2 4)	(23; 9; 1 1 3 1 4 4 3)	(25; 4; 1 1 2 2 3 6 2)
(21; 10; 1 1 4 1 4 4 2)	(23; 10; 1 1 3 3 1 4 4)	(25; 5; 1 1 2 2 6 2 3)
(21; 11; 1 1 4 2 1 4 4)	(23; 11; 1 1 3 3 4 1 4)	(25; 6; 1 1 2 2 6 3 2)
(21; 12; 1 1 4 2 4 1 4)	(23; 12; 1 1 3 4 1 3 4)	(25; 7; 1 1 2 3 2 2 6)
(21; 13; 1 1 4 4 1 2 4)	(23; 13; 1 1 3 4 1 4 3)	(25; 8; 1 1 2 3 2 6 2)
(21; 14; 1 1 4 4 1 4 2)	(23; 14; 1 1 3 4 3 1 4)	(25; 9; 1 1 2 3 6 2 2)

(25 ; 10 ; 1 1 2 6 2 2 3)	(25 ; 58 ; 1 3 2 1 6 2 2)	(26 ; 42 ; 1 2 2 2 5 1 4)
(25 ; 11 ; 1 1 2 6 2 3 2)	(25 ; 59 ; 1 3 2 2 1 6 2)	(26 ; 43 ; 1 2 2 4 1 2 5)
(25 ; 12 ; 1 1 2 6 3 2 2)	(25 ; 60 ; 1 3 2 2 2 1 6)	(26 ; 44 ; 1 2 2 4 1 5 2)
(25 ; 13 ; 1 1 3 2 2 2 6)		(26 ; 45 ; 1 2 2 4 2 1 5)
(25 ; 14 ; 1 1 3 2 2 6 2)	hyper n° 26 ; val.: 1 1 2 2 2 4 5 ;	(26 ; 46 ; 1 2 2 5 1 2 4)
(25 ; 15 ; 1 1 3 2 6 2 2)	RC = 8316	(26 ; 47 ; 1 2 2 5 1 4 2)
(25 ; 16 ; 1 1 3 6 2 2 2)	sys.: 60 ; imin = 1 ; imax_hyp = 5	(26 ; 48 ; 1 2 2 5 2 1 4)
(25 ; 17 ; 1 1 6 2 2 2 3)	(26 ; 1 ; 1 1 2 2 2 4 5)	(26 ; 49 ; 1 2 4 1 2 5 2)
(25 ; 18 ; 1 1 6 2 2 3 2)	(26 ; 2 ; 1 1 2 2 2 5 4)	(26 ; 50 ; 1 2 4 1 5 2 2)
(25 ; 19 ; 1 1 6 2 3 2 2)	(26 ; 3 ; 1 1 2 2 4 2 5)	(26 ; 51 ; 1 2 4 2 1 2 5)
(25 ; 20 ; 1 1 6 3 2 2 2)	(26 ; 4 ; 1 1 2 2 4 5 2)	(26 ; 52 ; 1 2 4 2 1 5 2)
(25 ; 21 ; 1 2 1 2 2 3 6)	(26 ; 5 ; 1 1 2 2 5 2 4)	(26 ; 53 ; 1 2 4 2 2 1 5)
(25 ; 22 ; 1 2 1 2 2 6 3)	(26 ; 6 ; 1 1 2 2 5 4 2)	(26 ; 54 ; 1 2 5 1 4 2 2)
(25 ; 23 ; 1 2 1 2 3 2 6)	(26 ; 7 ; 1 1 2 4 2 2 5)	(26 ; 55 ; 1 2 5 2 1 4 2)
(25 ; 24 ; 1 2 1 2 3 6 2)	(26 ; 8 ; 1 1 2 4 2 5 2)	(26 ; 56 ; 1 2 5 2 2 1 4)
(25 ; 25 ; 1 2 1 2 6 2 3)	(26 ; 9 ; 1 1 2 4 5 2 2)	(26 ; 57 ; 1 4 1 5 2 2 2)
(25 ; 26 ; 1 2 1 2 6 3 2)	(26 ; 10 ; 1 1 2 5 2 2 4)	(26 ; 58 ; 1 4 2 1 5 2 2)
(25 ; 27 ; 1 2 1 3 2 2 6)	(26 ; 11 ; 1 1 2 5 2 4 2)	(26 ; 59 ; 1 4 2 2 1 5 2)
(25 ; 28 ; 1 2 1 3 2 6 2)	(26 ; 12 ; 1 1 2 5 4 2 2)	(26 ; 60 ; 1 4 2 2 2 1 5)
(25 ; 29 ; 1 2 1 3 6 2 2)	(26 ; 13 ; 1 1 4 2 2 2 5)	
(25 ; 30 ; 1 2 1 6 2 2 3)	(26 ; 14 ; 1 1 4 2 2 5 2)	hyper n° 27 ; val.: 1 1 2 2 3 3 5 ;
(25 ; 31 ; 1 2 1 6 2 3 2)	(26 ; 15 ; 1 1 4 2 5 2 2)	RC = 9900
(25 ; 32 ; 1 2 1 6 3 2 2)	(26 ; 16 ; 1 1 4 5 2 2 2)	sys.: 90 ; imin = 1 ; imax_hyp = 5
(25 ; 33 ; 1 2 2 1 2 3 6)	(26 ; 17 ; 1 1 5 2 2 2 4)	(27 ; 1 ; 1 1 2 2 3 3 5)
(25 ; 34 ; 1 2 2 1 2 6 3)	(26 ; 18 ; 1 1 5 2 2 4 2)	(27 ; 2 ; 1 1 2 2 3 5 3)
(25 ; 35 ; 1 2 2 1 3 2 6)	(26 ; 19 ; 1 1 5 2 4 2 2)	(27 ; 3 ; 1 1 2 2 5 3 3)
(25 ; 36 ; 1 2 2 1 3 6 2)	(26 ; 20 ; 1 1 5 4 2 2 2)	(27 ; 4 ; 1 1 2 3 2 3 5)
(25 ; 37 ; 1 2 2 1 6 2 3)	(26 ; 21 ; 1 2 1 2 2 4 5)	(27 ; 5 ; 1 1 2 3 2 5 3)
(25 ; 38 ; 1 2 2 1 6 3 2)	(26 ; 22 ; 1 2 1 2 2 5 4)	(27 ; 6 ; 1 1 2 3 3 2 5)
(25 ; 39 ; 1 2 2 2 1 3 6)	(26 ; 23 ; 1 2 1 2 4 2 5)	(27 ; 7 ; 1 1 2 3 3 5 2)
(25 ; 40 ; 1 2 2 2 1 6 3)	(26 ; 24 ; 1 2 1 2 4 5 2)	(27 ; 8 ; 1 1 2 3 5 2 3)
(25 ; 41 ; 1 2 2 2 3 1 6)	(26 ; 25 ; 1 2 1 2 5 2 4)	(27 ; 9 ; 1 1 2 3 5 3 2)
(25 ; 42 ; 1 2 2 2 6 1 3)	(26 ; 26 ; 1 2 1 2 5 4 2)	(27 ; 10 ; 1 1 2 5 2 3 3)
(25 ; 43 ; 1 2 2 3 1 2 6)	(26 ; 27 ; 1 2 1 4 2 2 5)	(27 ; 11 ; 1 1 2 5 3 2 3)
(25 ; 44 ; 1 2 2 3 1 6 2)	(26 ; 28 ; 1 2 1 4 2 5 2)	(27 ; 12 ; 1 1 2 5 3 3 2)
(25 ; 45 ; 1 2 2 3 2 1 6)	(26 ; 29 ; 1 2 1 4 5 2 2)	(27 ; 13 ; 1 1 3 2 2 3 5)
(25 ; 46 ; 1 2 2 6 1 2 3)	(26 ; 30 ; 1 2 1 5 2 2 4)	(27 ; 14 ; 1 1 3 2 2 5 3)
(25 ; 47 ; 1 2 2 6 1 3 2)	(26 ; 31 ; 1 2 1 5 2 4 2)	(27 ; 15 ; 1 1 3 2 3 2 5)
(25 ; 48 ; 1 2 2 6 2 1 3)	(26 ; 32 ; 1 2 1 5 4 2 2)	(27 ; 16 ; 1 1 3 2 3 5 2)
(25 ; 49 ; 1 2 3 1 2 6 2)	(26 ; 33 ; 1 2 2 1 2 4 5)	(27 ; 17 ; 1 1 3 2 5 2 3)
(25 ; 50 ; 1 2 3 1 6 2 2)	(26 ; 34 ; 1 2 2 1 2 5 4)	(27 ; 18 ; 1 1 3 2 5 3 2)
(25 ; 51 ; 1 2 3 2 1 2 6)	(26 ; 35 ; 1 2 2 1 4 2 5)	(27 ; 19 ; 1 1 3 3 2 2 5)
(25 ; 52 ; 1 2 3 2 1 6 2)	(26 ; 36 ; 1 2 2 1 4 5 2)	(27 ; 20 ; 1 1 3 3 2 5 2)
(25 ; 53 ; 1 2 3 2 2 1 6)	(26 ; 37 ; 1 2 2 1 5 2 4)	(27 ; 21 ; 1 1 3 3 5 2 2)
(25 ; 54 ; 1 2 6 1 3 2 2)	(26 ; 38 ; 1 2 2 1 5 4 2)	(27 ; 22 ; 1 1 3 5 2 2 3)
(25 ; 55 ; 1 2 6 2 1 3 2)	(26 ; 39 ; 1 2 2 2 1 4 5)	(27 ; 23 ; 1 1 3 5 2 3 2)
(25 ; 56 ; 1 2 6 2 2 1 3)	(26 ; 40 ; 1 2 2 2 1 5 4)	(27 ; 24 ; 1 1 3 5 3 2 2)
(25 ; 57 ; 1 3 1 6 2 2 2)	(26 ; 41 ; 1 2 2 2 4 1 5)	(27 ; 25 ; 1 1 5 2 2 3 3)

(27; 26; 1 1 5 2 3 2 3)	(27; 74; 1 3 1 3 2 5 2)	(28; 28; 1 1 4 4 2 2 3)
(27; 27; 1 1 5 2 3 3 2)	(27; 75; 1 3 1 3 5 2 2)	(28; 29; 1 1 4 4 2 3 2)
(27; 28; 1 1 5 3 2 2 3)	(27; 76; 1 3 1 5 2 2 3)	(28; 30; 1 1 4 4 3 2 2)
(27; 29; 1 1 5 3 2 3 2)	(27; 77; 1 3 1 5 2 3 2)	(28; 31; 1 2 1 2 3 4 4)
(27; 30; 1 1 5 3 3 2 2)	(27; 78; 1 3 1 5 3 2 2)	(28; 32; 1 2 1 2 4 3 4)
(27; 31; 1 2 1 2 3 3 5)	(27; 79; 1 3 2 1 3 2 5)	(28; 33; 1 2 1 2 4 4 3)
(27; 32; 1 2 1 2 3 5 3)	(27; 80; 1 3 2 1 3 5 2)	(28; 34; 1 2 1 3 2 4 4)
(27; 33; 1 2 1 2 5 3 3)	(27; 81; 1 3 2 1 5 2 3)	(28; 35; 1 2 1 3 4 2 4)
(27; 34; 1 2 1 3 2 3 5)	(27; 82; 1 3 2 1 5 3 2)	(28; 36; 1 2 1 3 4 4 2)
(27; 35; 1 2 1 3 2 5 3)	(27; 83; 1 3 2 2 1 3 5)	(28; 37; 1 2 1 4 2 3 4)
(27; 36; 1 2 1 3 3 2 5)	(27; 84; 1 3 2 2 1 5 3)	(28; 38; 1 2 1 4 2 4 3)
(27; 37; 1 2 1 3 3 5 2)	(27; 85; 1 3 2 2 3 1 5)	(28; 39; 1 2 1 4 3 2 4)
(27; 38; 1 2 1 3 5 2 3)	(27; 86; 1 3 2 3 1 5 2)	(28; 40; 1 2 1 4 3 4 2)
(27; 39; 1 2 1 3 5 3 2)	(27; 87; 1 3 2 3 2 1 5)	(28; 41; 1 2 1 4 4 2 3)
(27; 40; 1 2 1 5 2 3 3)	(27; 88; 1 3 3 1 5 2 2)	(28; 42; 1 2 1 4 4 3 2)
(27; 41; 1 2 1 5 3 2 3)	(27; 89; 1 3 3 2 1 5 2)	(28; 43; 1 2 2 1 3 4 4)
(27; 42; 1 2 1 5 3 3 2)	(27; 90; 1 3 3 2 2 1 5)	(28; 44; 1 2 2 1 4 3 4)
(27; 43; 1 2 2 1 3 3 5)		(28; 45; 1 2 2 1 4 4 3)
(27; 44; 1 2 2 1 3 5 3)	hyper n° 28; val.: 1 1 2 2 3 4 4;	(28; 46; 1 2 2 3 1 4 4)
(27; 45; 1 2 2 1 5 3 3)	RC = 8820	(28; 47; 1 2 2 3 4 1 4)
(27; 46; 1 2 2 3 1 3 5)	sys.: 90; imin = 1; imax_hyp = 4	(28; 48; 1 2 2 4 1 3 4)
(27; 47; 1 2 2 3 1 5 3)	(28; 1; 1 1 2 2 3 4 4)	(28; 49; 1 2 2 4 1 4 3)
(27; 48; 1 2 2 3 3 1 5)	(28; 2; 1 1 2 2 4 3 4)	(28; 50; 1 2 2 4 3 1 4)
(27; 49; 1 2 2 3 5 1 3)	(28; 3; 1 1 2 2 4 4 3)	(28; 51; 1 2 2 4 4 1 3)
(27; 50; 1 2 2 5 1 3 3)	(28; 4; 1 1 2 3 2 4 4)	(28; 52; 1 2 3 1 2 4 4)
(27; 51; 1 2 2 5 3 1 3)	(28; 5; 1 1 2 3 4 2 4)	(28; 53; 1 2 3 1 4 2 4)
(27; 52; 1 2 3 1 2 3 5)	(28; 6; 1 1 2 3 4 4 2)	(28; 54; 1 2 3 1 4 4 2)
(27; 53; 1 2 3 1 2 5 3)	(28; 7; 1 1 2 4 2 3 4)	(28; 55; 1 2 3 2 1 4 4)
(27; 54; 1 2 3 1 3 2 5)	(28; 8; 1 1 2 4 2 4 3)	(28; 56; 1 2 3 2 4 1 4)
(27; 55; 1 2 3 1 3 5 2)	(28; 9; 1 1 2 4 3 2 4)	(28; 57; 1 2 3 4 1 2 4)
(27; 56; 1 2 3 1 5 2 3)	(28; 10; 1 1 2 4 3 4 2)	(28; 58; 1 2 3 4 1 4 2)
(27; 57; 1 2 3 1 5 3 2)	(28; 11; 1 1 2 4 4 2 3)	(28; 59; 1 2 3 4 2 1 4)
(27; 58; 1 2 3 2 1 3 5)	(28; 12; 1 1 2 4 4 3 2)	(28; 60; 1 2 4 1 2 4 3)
(27; 59; 1 2 3 2 1 5 3)	(28; 13; 1 1 3 2 2 4 4)	(28; 61; 1 2 4 1 3 2 4)
(27; 60; 1 2 3 2 3 1 5)	(28; 14; 1 1 3 2 4 2 4)	(28; 62; 1 2 4 1 3 4 2)
(27; 61; 1 2 3 2 5 1 3)	(28; 15; 1 1 3 2 4 4 2)	(28; 63; 1 2 4 1 4 2 3)
(27; 62; 1 2 3 3 1 2 5)	(28; 16; 1 1 3 4 2 2 4)	(28; 64; 1 2 4 1 4 3 2)
(27; 63; 1 2 3 3 1 5 2)	(28; 17; 1 1 3 4 2 4 2)	(28; 65; 1 2 4 2 1 3 4)
(27; 64; 1 2 3 3 2 1 5)	(28; 18; 1 1 3 4 4 2 2)	(28; 66; 1 2 4 2 1 4 3)
(27; 65; 1 2 3 5 1 3 2)	(28; 19; 1 1 4 2 2 3 4)	(28; 67; 1 2 4 2 3 1 4)
(27; 66; 1 2 3 5 2 1 3)	(28; 20; 1 1 4 2 2 4 3)	(28; 68; 1 2 4 2 4 1 3)
(27; 67; 1 2 5 1 3 2 3)	(28; 21; 1 1 4 2 3 2 4)	(28; 69; 1 2 4 3 1 4 2)
(27; 68; 1 2 5 1 3 3 2)	(28; 22; 1 1 4 2 3 4 2)	(28; 70; 1 2 4 3 2 1 4)
(27; 69; 1 2 5 2 1 3 3)	(28; 23; 1 1 4 2 4 2 3)	(28; 71; 1 2 4 4 1 3 2)
(27; 70; 1 2 5 2 3 1 3)	(28; 24; 1 1 4 2 4 3 2)	(28; 72; 1 2 4 4 2 1 3)
(27; 71; 1 2 5 3 1 3 2)	(28; 25; 1 1 4 3 2 2 4)	(28; 73; 1 3 1 4 2 2 4)
(27; 72; 1 2 5 3 2 1 3)	(28; 26; 1 1 4 3 2 4 2)	(28; 74; 1 3 1 4 2 4 2)
(27; 73; 1 3 1 3 2 2 5)	(28; 27; 1 1 4 3 4 2 2)	(28; 75; 1 3 1 4 4 2 2)

(28; 76; 1 3 2 1 4 2 4)	(29; 30; 1 2 3 3 3 1 4)	hyper n° 32; val.: 1 2 2 2 2 3 5;
(28; 77; 1 3 2 1 4 4 2)	(29; 31; 1 2 3 3 4 1 3)	RC = 8910
(28; 78; 1 3 2 2 1 4 4)	(29; 32; 1 2 3 4 1 3 3)	sys.: 30; imin = 1; imax_hyp = 5
(28; 79; 1 3 2 2 4 1 4)	(29; 33; 1 2 3 4 3 1 3)	(32; 1; 1 2 2 2 2 3 5)
(28; 80; 1 3 2 4 1 4 2)	(29; 34; 1 2 4 1 3 3 3)	(32; 2; 1 2 2 2 2 5 3)
(28; 81; 1 3 2 4 2 1 4)	(29; 35; 1 2 4 3 1 3 3)	(32; 3; 1 2 2 2 3 2 5)
(28; 82; 1 3 4 1 4 2 2)	(29; 36; 1 2 4 3 3 1 3)	(32; 4; 1 2 2 2 3 5 2)
(28; 83; 1 3 4 2 1 4 2)	(29; 37; 1 3 1 3 2 3 4)	(32; 5; 1 2 2 2 5 2 3)
(28; 84; 1 3 4 2 2 1 4)	(29; 38; 1 3 1 3 2 4 3)	(32; 6; 1 2 2 2 5 3 2)
(28; 85; 1 4 1 4 2 2 3)	(29; 39; 1 3 1 3 3 2 4)	(32; 7; 1 2 2 3 2 2 5)
(28; 86; 1 4 1 4 2 3 2)	(29; 40; 1 3 1 3 3 4 2)	(32; 8; 1 2 2 3 2 5 2)
(28; 87; 1 4 1 4 3 2 2)	(29; 41; 1 3 1 3 4 2 3)	(32; 9; 1 2 2 3 5 2 2)
(28; 88; 1 4 2 1 4 2 3)	(29; 42; 1 3 1 3 4 3 2)	(32; 10; 1 2 2 5 2 2 3)
(28; 89; 1 4 2 1 4 3 2)	(29; 43; 1 3 1 4 2 3 3)	(32; 11; 1 2 2 5 2 3 2)
(28; 90; 1 4 2 2 1 4 3)	(29; 44; 1 3 1 4 3 2 3)	(32; 12; 1 2 2 5 3 2 2)
hyper n° 29; val.: 1 1 2 3 3 3 4;	(29; 45; 1 3 1 4 3 3 2)	(32; 13; 1 2 3 2 2 2 5)
RC = 10500	(29; 46; 1 3 2 1 3 3 4)	(32; 14; 1 2 3 2 2 5 2)
sys.: 60; imin = 1; imax_hyp = 4	(29; 47; 1 3 2 1 3 4 3)	(32; 15; 1 2 3 2 5 2 2)
(29; 1; 1 1 2 3 3 3 4)	(29; 48; 1 3 2 1 4 3 3)	(32; 16; 1 2 3 5 2 2 2)
(29; 2; 1 1 2 3 3 4 3)	(29; 49; 1 3 2 3 1 3 4)	(32; 17; 1 2 5 2 2 2 3)
(29; 3; 1 1 2 3 4 3 3)	(29; 50; 1 3 2 3 1 4 3)	(32; 18; 1 2 5 2 2 3 2)
(29; 4; 1 1 2 4 3 3 3)	(29; 51; 1 3 2 3 3 1 4)	(32; 19; 1 2 5 2 3 2 2)
(29; 5; 1 1 3 2 3 3 4)	(29; 52; 1 3 2 4 1 3 3)	(32; 20; 1 2 5 3 2 2 2)
(29; 6; 1 1 3 2 3 4 3)	(29; 53; 1 3 3 1 3 4 2)	(32; 21; 1 3 2 2 2 2 5)
(29; 7; 1 1 3 2 4 3 3)	(29; 54; 1 3 3 1 4 2 3)	(32; 22; 1 3 2 2 2 5 2)
(29; 8; 1 1 3 3 2 3 4)	(29; 55; 1 3 3 1 4 3 2)	(32; 23; 1 3 2 2 5 2 2)
(29; 9; 1 1 3 3 2 4 3)	(29; 56; 1 3 3 2 1 3 4)	(32; 24; 1 3 2 5 2 2 2)
(29; 10; 1 1 3 3 3 2 4)	(29; 57; 1 3 3 2 1 4 3)	(32; 25; 1 3 5 2 2 2 2)
(29; 11; 1 1 3 3 3 4 2)	(29; 58; 1 3 3 2 3 1 4)	(32; 26; 1 5 2 2 2 2 3)
(29; 12; 1 1 3 3 4 2 3)	(29; 59; 1 3 3 3 1 4 2)	(32; 27; 1 5 2 2 2 3 2)
(29; 13; 1 1 3 3 4 3 2)	(29; 60; 1 3 3 3 2 1 4)	(32; 28; 1 5 2 2 3 2 2)
(29; 14; 1 1 3 4 2 3 3)	hyper n° 30; val.: 1 1 3 3 3 3 3;	(32; 29; 1 5 2 3 2 2 2)
(29; 15; 1 1 3 4 3 2 3)	RC = 12500	(32; 30; 1 5 3 2 2 2 2)
(29; 16; 1 1 3 4 3 3 2)	sys.: 3; imin = 1; imax_hyp = 3	hyper n° 33; val.: 1 2 2 2 2 4 4;
(29; 17; 1 1 4 2 3 3 3)	(30; 1; 1 1 3 3 3 3 3)	RC = 7938
(29; 18; 1 1 4 3 2 3 3)	(30; 2; 1 3 1 3 3 3 3)	sys.: 15; imin = 1; imax_hyp = 4
(29; 19; 1 1 4 3 3 2 3)	(30; 3; 1 3 3 1 3 3 3)	(33; 1; 1 2 2 2 2 4 4)
(29; 20; 1 1 4 3 3 3 2)		(33; 2; 1 2 2 2 4 2 4)
(29; 21; 1 2 1 3 3 3 4)	hyper n° 31; val.: 1 2 2 2 2 2 6;	(33; 3; 1 2 2 2 4 4 2)
(29; 22; 1 2 1 3 3 4 3)	RC = 6318	(33; 4; 1 2 2 4 2 2 4)
(29; 23; 1 2 1 3 4 3 3)	sys.: 6; imin = 1; imax_hyp = 6	(33; 5; 1 2 2 4 2 4 2)
(29; 24; 1 2 1 4 3 3 3)	(31; 1; 1 2 2 2 2 2 6)	(33; 6; 1 2 2 4 4 2 2)
(29; 25; 1 2 3 1 3 3 4)	(31; 2; 1 2 2 2 2 6 2)	(33; 7; 1 2 4 2 2 2 4)
(29; 26; 1 2 3 1 3 4 3)	(31; 3; 1 2 2 2 6 2 2)	(33; 8; 1 2 4 2 2 4 2)
(29; 27; 1 2 3 1 4 3 3)	(31; 4; 1 2 2 6 2 2 2)	(33; 9; 1 2 4 2 4 2 2)
(29; 28; 1 2 3 3 1 3 4)	(31; 5; 1 2 6 2 2 2 2)	(33; 10; 1 2 4 4 2 2 2)
(29; 29; 1 2 3 3 1 4 3)	(31; 6; 1 6 2 2 2 2 2)	(33; 11; 1 4 2 2 2 2 4)

(33; 12; 1 4 2 2 2 4 2)	(34; 41; 1 3 2 4 2 3 2)	hyper n° 37; val.: 2 2 2 2 2 3 4;
(33; 13; 1 4 2 2 4 2 2)	(34; 42; 1 3 2 4 3 2 2)	RC = 8505
(33; 14; 1 4 2 4 2 2 2)	(34; 43; 1 3 3 2 2 2 4)	sys.: 6; imin = 1; imax_hyp = 4
(33; 15; 1 4 4 2 2 2 2)	(34; 44; 1 3 3 2 2 4 2)	(37; 1; 2 2 2 2 2 3 4)
hyper n° 34; val.: 1 2 2 2 3 3 4;	(34; 45; 1 3 3 2 4 2 2)	(37; 2; 2 2 2 2 2 4 3)
RC = 9450	(34; 46; 1 3 3 4 2 2 2)	(37; 3; 2 2 2 2 3 2 4)
sys.: 60; imin = 1; imax_hyp = 4	(34; 47; 1 3 4 2 2 2 3)	(37; 4; 2 2 2 2 4 2 3)
(34; 1; 1 2 2 2 3 3 4)	(34; 48; 1 3 4 2 2 3 2)	(37; 5; 2 2 2 3 2 2 4)
(34; 2; 1 2 2 2 3 4 3)	(34; 49; 1 3 4 2 3 2 2)	(37; 6; 2 2 2 4 2 2 3)
(34; 3; 1 2 2 2 4 3 3)	(34; 50; 1 3 4 3 2 2 2)	hyper n° 38; val.: 2 2 2 2 3 3 3;
(34; 4; 1 2 2 3 2 3 4)	(34; 51; 1 4 2 2 2 3 3)	RC = 10125
(34; 5; 1 2 2 3 2 4 3)	(34; 52; 1 4 2 2 3 2 3)	sys.: 5; imin = 1; imax_hyp = 3
(34; 6; 1 2 2 3 3 2 4)	(34; 53; 1 4 2 2 3 3 2)	(38; 1; 2 2 2 2 3 3 3)
(34; 7; 1 2 2 3 3 4 2)	(34; 54; 1 4 2 3 2 2 3)	(38; 2; 2 2 2 3 2 3 3)
(34; 8; 1 2 2 3 4 2 3)	(34; 55; 1 4 2 3 2 3 2)	(38; 3; 2 2 2 3 3 2 3)
(34; 9; 1 2 2 3 4 3 2)	(34; 56; 1 4 2 3 3 2 2)	(38; 4; 2 2 3 2 2 3 3)
(34; 10; 1 2 2 4 2 3 3)	(34; 57; 1 4 3 2 2 2 3)	(38; 5; 2 2 3 2 3 2 3)
(34; 11; 1 2 2 4 3 2 3)	(34; 58; 1 4 3 2 2 3 2)	
(34; 12; 1 2 2 4 3 3 2)	(34; 59; 1 4 3 2 3 2 2)	
(34; 13; 1 2 3 2 2 3 4)	(34; 60; 1 4 3 3 2 2 2)	
(34; 14; 1 2 3 2 2 4 3)	hyper n° 35; val.: 1 2 2 3 3 3 3;	
(34; 15; 1 2 3 2 3 2 4)	RC = 11250	
(34; 16; 1 2 3 2 3 4 2)	sys.: 15; imin = 1; imax_hyp = 3	
(34; 17; 1 2 3 2 4 2 3)	(35; 1; 1 2 2 3 3 3 3)	
(34; 18; 1 2 3 2 4 3 2)	(35; 2; 1 2 3 2 3 3 3)	
(34; 19; 1 2 3 3 2 2 4)	(35; 3; 1 2 3 3 2 3 3)	
(34; 20; 1 2 3 3 2 4 2)	(35; 4; 1 2 3 3 3 2 3)	
(34; 21; 1 2 3 3 4 2 2)	(35; 5; 1 2 3 3 3 3 2)	
(34; 22; 1 2 3 4 2 2 3)	(35; 6; 1 3 2 2 3 3 3)	
(34; 23; 1 2 3 4 2 3 2)	(35; 7; 1 3 2 3 2 3 3)	
(34; 24; 1 2 3 4 3 2 2)	(35; 8; 1 3 2 3 3 2 3)	
(34; 25; 1 2 4 2 2 3 3)	(35; 9; 1 3 2 3 3 3 2)	
(34; 26; 1 2 4 2 3 2 3)	(35; 10; 1 3 3 2 2 3 3)	
(34; 27; 1 2 4 2 3 3 2)	(35; 11; 1 3 3 2 3 2 3)	
(34; 28; 1 2 4 3 2 2 3)	(35; 12; 1 3 3 2 3 3 2)	
(34; 29; 1 2 4 3 2 3 2)	(35; 13; 1 3 3 3 2 2 3)	
(34; 30; 1 2 4 3 3 2 2)	(35; 14; 1 3 3 3 2 3 2)	
(34; 31; 1 3 2 2 2 3 4)	(35; 15; 1 3 3 3 3 2 2)	
(34; 32; 1 3 2 2 2 4 3)	hyper n° 36; val.: 2 2 2 2 2 2 5;	
(34; 33; 1 3 2 2 3 2 4)	RC = 8019	
(34; 34; 1 3 2 2 3 4 2)	sys.: 1; imin = 1; imax_hyp = 5	
(34; 35; 1 3 2 2 4 2 3)	(36; 1; 2 2 2 2 2 2 5)	
(34; 36; 1 3 2 2 4 3 2)		
(34; 37; 1 3 2 3 2 2 4)		
(34; 38; 1 3 2 3 2 4 2)		
(34; 39; 1 3 2 3 4 2 2)		
(34; 40; 1 3 2 4 2 2 3)		